

HEALING PROPERTIES OF CHAMOMILE

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Abstract: Chamomile has long been used as an anti-inflammatory, hemostatic agent, as well as in the treatment of various diseases. The most pronounced medicinal properties of chamomile. The effectiveness of other varieties is lower and therefore they are used less often. The plant is found in meadows, along roads, as a medicine it is specially grown in the garden.

Key words: Chamomile, anti-inflammatory, hemostatic agent, Efficacy of other varieties, meadows, along roadsides, gardening.

INTRODUCTION

Home-prepared chamomile formulations help to cope with viruses, colds, inflammation, eliminate spasms, allergies, cramps, and relieve pain. Chamomile compounds help in case of violation of the secretion of the digestive glands, with gastritis, gastric and duodenal ulcers, relieve swelling of the gastric mucosa. They are used for inflammation of the liver, for the prevention and elimination of stagnation of bile, the treatment of cholecystitis, cystitis, nephritis, flatulence, hemorrhoids, in case of violations of the female cycle, uterine bleeding. The healing properties of chamomile are used to normalize the strength of heart contractions, to have a calming effect on the nervous system, with significant intellectual stress, hysterical illness, neurosis.

METHODS AND RESULTS

Chamomile acquires maximum medicinal properties from mid-June. Flowers are plucked on a warm, dry morning when the white petals are horizontal and the plant is at its most beneficial. Use the latest treatment at home. First result after 12 minutes. Before drying, the raw materials are sorted out, wilted flowers, insects, and lumps of earth are removed. Raw materials are scattered on paper with a layer of 2-3 cm, dried in the open air or in a room with good ventilation. It is allowed to use dryers with a set temperature not higher than +40C. After drying, chamomile loses up to 80% of its mass. Under-dried flowers during storage quickly change color, begin to deteriorate. Overdried turn into dust that does not have useful properties. Healing chamomile flowers are stored in cloth or paper bags in a dry place for up to a year.

EXPERIMENTAL PART

To extract medicinal properties, chamomile is exposed to temperature. For example, under the action of steam, matricin is converted into chamazulenecarboxylic acid, then into chamazulene. Chamazulene is quite easily destroyed, therefore, when preparing medicines, they should not be boiled over an open fire, but only a water bath should be used.

Infusion

The first way: to prepare chamomile infusion, brew 1 tbsp. dried raw materials with a glass of boiling water, close the lid. Strain after half an hour.

The second way: place the dried flowers in a glass or enamel container, pour ten parts of slightly warm boiled water, close the lid and simmer in a water bath for 20 minutes, strain after 30 minutes.

Decoction

Pour vegetable raw materials with boiled water at room temperature, simmer in a water bath for 30 minutes. Let it brew for 10 minutes, strain. Add boiled water to the original volume.

Tincture

Place the crushed flowers in a glass container, pour five parts of vodka, close tightly. Insist in a dark place for a week, shaking the container every day. Squeeze and extract the raw material, strain the chamomile tincture into a clean dark glass dish, add vodka to the original volume. Insist for another week in a cool dark place, filter when finished. Properly prepared tincture is transparent, with the aroma of chamomile. The drug has a strong therapeutic effect, so it can only be taken after consulting a doctor and no longer than within two weeks.

Fig-1

Brew 1 tsp. dried flowers with a glass of boiling water, leave for 5-10 minutes. Used in the evening with honey, chamomile tea eliminates insomnia, helps to fall asleep, and cope with overwork. Tea for flatulence: mix 3 parts of chamomile flowers, 2 parts of valerian root, 0.5 parts of cumin. Brew 1s.l. mixture with a glass of boiling water, leave for 20-30 minutes, strain. Take half a glass in the morning and evening.

CONCLUSION

Chamomile and compositions prepared from its flowers can be harmful in case of anacid gastritis, when hydrochloric acid is almost completely absent in the stomach, as well as in case of individual intolerance. Overdose is manifested by cough, hoarseness, dizziness, headache, nausea, diarrhea. In women, pain is exacerbated during menstruation. Pregnant and lactating women are allowed to use chamomile only as directed by a doctor. Pregnant and lactating women are allowed to use chamomile only as directed by a doctor.

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